

Computational study on the encapsulation of *o*-phenylenediamine, *m*-phenylenediamine and *p*-phenylenediamine into the host cucurbit[7]uril

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Abstract : The structural investigation of *o*-phenylenediamine (*o*PA), *m*-phenylenediamine (*m*PA), and *p*-phenylenediamine (*p*PA) encapsulated with the host cucurbit[7]uril (CB[7]) were performed by computational method using Semi-empirical PM3 method. The calculation was applied for only 1 : 1 stoichiometric complexes between CB[7] and PAs. CB[7] and PAs formed weak inclusion complexes. The CB[7] host molecule showed a slight geometrical flexibility in PAs binding which allowed an induced fit of the PAs. In the inclusion complex, these molecules were found to be deep inside the cavity, with the formation of hydrogen bonding between the portal oxygen atoms and the amino group of the guest molecules.

Keywords : Phenylenediamines, cucurbit[7]uril, Semi-empirical PM3 method, host-guest complex.

Introduction

Noncovalent supramolecular interactions are omnipresent in nature. The fundamental study of these noncovalent interactions has occupied the forefront of contemporary research as they have been judiciously used in a wide range of applications including the development of catalysts, stationary phases in chromatographic separations, sequestration of different metal ions from solutions, chemical sensors, self assembly of nanomaterials, and drug development¹⁻⁴. All of these applications require the availability of receptors, natural or non-natural oligomers and polymers or solid-state hosts, that interact with their guests with high affinity through highly selective binding processes. In response, supramolecular chemists have designed, synthesized, and evaluated the recognition properties of a wide variety of non-natural receptors including cyclodextrins, crown ethers, calixarenes, and cyclophanes that display exceptional affinities and selectivities⁵.

Of late, members of a new class of supramolecular hosts called cucurbit[*n*]urils (CB[*n*]) which are composed of glycoluril units linked by a pair of methylene groups and have fairly rigid hydrophobic cavities of low polarizability, have been synthesized⁶. They have been used as efficient hosts⁷ that can be accessed through their carbo-

nyl-lined portals. The cavity sizes of CB[*n*] hosts and their derivatives exceed the range available with the widely studied α -, β - and γ -cyclodextrins. Among CB[*n*] family, cucurbit[7]uril (CB[7]) has substantially higher water solubility than CB[6] and CB[8], as well as a more voluminous cavity than its water-soluble analogue CB[5], and can thus bind a wider range of guests in aqueous solutions. In addition to the usual hydrophobic effect in water, which favors inclusion of organic guests within the CB[7] cavity, CB[7] provides another distinct supramolecular interaction, namely, ion-dipole interactions at carbonyl-lined portals, that promotes the binding of the cationic sites of organic guests. Recently, CB[7] host was used to form strong and stable inclusion complexes with some fluorescent dyes⁸⁻¹⁰ to improve their fluorescence yields and photochemical stabilities in water, which also led to other novel applications such as operation of efficient and photostable aqueous dye lasers¹¹. Moreover, the low toxicity of CBs¹² including a high cell tolerance in living biological systems at a concentration of up to 1 mM indicating their potential use as molecular containers in advanced drug-delivery systems has been demonstrated.

In this paper, the investigation of structure and interaction of host-guest complexes of CB[7] with PAs in gas phase is performed using Gaussian 09W program. Such

computational works of the inclusion complexes were not performed in the earlier studies. The formation of host-guest complexes between drug molecules and cyclodextrins reported earlier, in connection with our previous theoretical efforts in designing new functional molecular systems¹³⁻¹⁹. The optimized structures of the inclusion complexes of PAs and CB[7] molecules have been arrived out and reported in the present work.

Computational methods :

The initial molecular geometry of CB[7] was obtained from X-ray diffraction data²⁰. The theoretical calculations were performed with Gaussian 09W package. The structures of CB[7], *o*-phenylenediamine, *m*-phenylenediamine and *p*-phenylenediamine are built with Spartan (version 8.0) and fully optimized by PM3 method without imposing any symmetrical restrictions. Full geometry optimizations for all systems were performed without symmetry constrains. For all optimized structures, normal mode frequencies were calculated and thermochemical analysis was performed. The absence of imaginary frequencies in the vibrational spectra demonstrated that the optimized structures correspond to minima on the potential energy surface rather than transition states.

Results and discussion

Optimized geometries :

In this study, only the inclusion complexes in molar proportion 1 : 1 are considered between one molecule of CB[7] and one molecule of PAs. Molecular modeling analysis has been performed for the complexation process of *o*PA, *m*PA and *p*PA within the CB[7] using PM3 method. The optimized structures of the guests, host and inclusion complexes are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. The optimized geometry of CB[7] is consistent with the earlier experimental and modeling results²¹. To determine the geometries of the possible PAs : CB[7] complexes, PAs were penetrated into the cavity of CB[7] and allowed to relax. Only one orientation of the guest molecules inside the cavity of CB[7] was considered since the two rims of CB[7] are equivalent. The depth of the cavity is about 6.27 Å in CB[7], but the equatorial width is 8.40 Å with ring size. The calculated intramolecular distance between the oxygen portals for CB[7] is 8.40 Å which are in agreement with the previously reported values²⁰.

The length of studied guest molecules is lower than that of the host molecule. The geometries of the inclusion complexes by PM3 method show that these guest molecules are deeply entrapped into the cavity of the host molecule.

Geometrical flexibility of CB[7] :

Table 1 summarizes the symmetry and intramolecular distance between oxygen portals and diameter of the oxygen portals. All inclusion complexes show a perfect C1 symmetry, i.e. the CB[7] host molecule is not distorted from its native symmetry. This accounts for the geometrical flexibility of CB[7] in these molecules binding²². From Table 1, it is evident that the guest molecules slightly affect the flexibility of the host molecule. The geometry of complexed CB[7] is compared to its native geometry in a significantly reduced intramolecular distance between the oxygen portals. The intramolecular distance of the oxygen portal for *o*PA and *p*PA is reduced from 6.26 to 6.01/6.18 Å whereas for *m*PA it is significantly increased from 6.26 to 6.78 Å. The distance of opposing oxygen atoms within a portal (the portal diameter) is slightly varied around 8.35–8.48 Å. The intramolecular distance between the oxygen portals are enlarged in one direction but are reduced in the perpendicular distance. This shows that CB[7] is a flexible host and could accommodate large guests. The amino groups of the guests lie on the plane of the portal oxygen atoms, with the possible existence of intermolecular hydrogen bonding.

HOMO-LUMO parameters :

The highest occupied molecular orbitals (HOMOs) and the lowest-lying unoccupied molecular orbitals (LUMOs) are named as frontier molecular orbitals (FMOs). The HOMO, LUMO energy structure of free guests, host, and inclusion complexes were shown in Fig. 3. The FMOs play an important role in the optical and electric properties, as well as in quantum chemistry and UV-Vis spectra²³. The HOMO represents the ability to donate an electron while LUMO as an electron acceptor represents the ability to obtain an electron. The energy gap between HOMO and LUMO determines the kinetic stability, chemical reactivity, optical polarizability, chemical hardness-softness of a molecule etc.^{24,25}. In order to evaluate the energetic behavior of the guests, host, and inclusion complexes, we carried out the calculations in gas phase. The

Fig. 1. The optimized structures of (a) *o*PA , (b) *m*PA, (c) *p*PA, (d) CB[7] and (e) glycouril monomer of CB[7].

calculated energy values of HOMO and energy gap of HOMO-LUMO for guests and host are more negative than those of the complexes. The LUMO values for guests and host are significantly positive than those of the complexes. The energy gap of HOMO-LUMO explains the eventual charge transfer interaction within the molecule, which influences the biological activity of the molecule. This electronic absorption corresponds to the transition from the ground to the first excited state and is mainly

described by one electron excitation from HOMO to LUMO. Consequently, the lowering of the HOMO-LUMO band gap is essentially a consequence of the large stabilization of the LUMO due to the strong electron-acceptor ability of the electron-acceptor group. The high HOMO-LUMO values for complexes indicate that the host molecule has less electron transfer with these guests due to the less electron-acceptor ability of the electron acceptor group.

Table 1. The properties of host molecule and inclusion complexes

Properties	CB[7]	<i>o</i> PA : CB[7]	<i>m</i> PA : CB[7]	<i>p</i> PA : CB[7]
Symmetry	C1	C1	C1	C1
Intramolecular distance between oxygene portals (Å)	6.26	6.01	6.78	6.18
Diameter of oxygene portal (Å)	8.40	8.41	8.35	8.48

Fig. 2. The lowest energy structure of (a) *o*PA : CB[7], (b) *m*PA : CB[7] and (c) *p*PA : CB[7].

From Table 2, it can be seen that the complexation of CB[7] with these molecules is equal and the stability of the inclusion complexes is the same. The energy gap between HOMO and LUMO of each complex suggests that there will be no significant change in the electronic spectrum of the guest molecules driving molecular recognition and binding. This suggests the stability of the above three molecules : CB[7] complexes is same. The HOMO of these molecules do not vary (Table 2 and Fig. 3) and indicates same complexation possible. However, the

HOMO-LUMO gap for *o*PA complex is more negative and suggests that this complex is more stable than other two complexes. The HOMO-LUMO energy structures for the complexes are shown in Fig. 4. The HOMO orbital is localized on the benzene ring and the LUMO orbital is localized on the cucurbituril unit in the PAs : CB[7] complex²⁶. For the PAs, the HOMO orbitals are observed on the benzene ring and amino group and the LUMO orbitals are observed on the benzene ring. These findings indicate an intense electronic interaction between

Table 2. Binding energies and HOMO, LUMO energy of *o*PA, *m*PA and *p*PA before and after complexation by PM3 method

Properties	<i>o</i> PA	<i>m</i> PA	<i>p</i> PA	CB[7]	<i>o</i> PA : CB[7]	<i>m</i> PA : CB[7]	<i>p</i> PA : CB[7]
E_{HOMO} (eV)	-8.23	-8.39	-8.05	-9.42	-7.28	-7.29	-6.90
E_{LUMO} (eV)	0.41	0.46	0.41	0.13	0.14	0.09	0.17
$E_{\text{HOMO}} - E_{\text{LUMO}}$ (eV)	-8.65	-8.85	-8.47	-9.55	-7.42	-7.39	-7.07
Dipole (D)	2.54	2.43	2.43	7.75	6.23	5.85	6.76
E (kcal mol ⁻¹)	22.20	19.17	19.66	-329.86	-309.67	-311.95	-312.90
ΔE (kcal mol ⁻¹)					-2.01	-1.26	-2.70

Fig. 3. The HOMO, LUMO energy structures of (a) *o*PA, (b) *m*PA, (c) *p*PA and (d) CB[7] before complexation.

CB[7] and PAs which account for the very high formation of energy involved in the complex formation.

The dipole moment of *o*PA is higher than those of *m*PA and *p*PA which have equal values (Table 2). The dipole moment of CB[7] is 7.75 D, *o*PA is 2.54 D, *m*PA is 2.43 D and *p*PA is 2.43 D. These values are lower than those of the complexes; i.e. *o*PA complex has 6.23 D, *m*PA complex has 5.85 D and *p*PA complex has 6.76 D. The dipole moments of *m*PA and *p*PA are not equal in

the complexes because the polarity of the host molecule changes the dipole moment value. This indicates that the polarity of the CB[7] cavity decreases after these molecules enter the cavity. The above quantum mechanical computation values demonstrate a strong relationship with the complexation behavior. One can therefore conclude that the dipole moment values show a strong correlation with the complexation behavior. However, it is not straightforward to answer why the complexation of CB[7]

Fig. 4. The HOMO, LUMO energy structures of (a) *o*PA, (b) *m*PA and (c) *p*PA after complexation.

with *p*PA is more favorable than with *o*PA and *m*PA if the dipole-dipole interaction and hydrophobic interaction are the driving forces in CB[7] complexation.

Binding energy :

Generally, the energy decreases systematically with formation of a host-guest aggregation. The decreased energy named the binding energy (BE) is related to the stability of the corresponding host-guest complex. A stable complex always gives a negative value of BE. The BE of the inclusion complexes for the complexation reaction is

given by eq. (1).

$$\Delta E_{\text{complexaton}} = E_{\text{complex}} - (E_{\text{CB[7]}} + E_{\text{PAs}}) \quad (1)$$

where E_{complex} , $E_{\text{CB[7]}}$ and E_{PAs} represent the total energy of the complex, the free optimized CB[7], and the free optimized molecules respectively. The three complexation energies are negative which demonstrate that the complexation of PAs in CB[7] are thermodynamically favorable. Generally, the inclusion complex with more negative binding energy is considered the most favored one. Among the three inclusion complexes, *p*PA :

CB[7] complex has the lowest energy ($-2.70 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$), next *o*PA ($-2.01 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) and then *m*PA ($-1.26 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$). This indicates that PAs forms weak inclusion complexes.

The optimized complexation structures in Fig. 2 demonstrate that hydrogen bond is formed in all the complexes. The intermolecular hydrogen bonds are formed between hydrogen atom of amino group of the PAs and portal oxygen atoms of CB[7] with a $d_{\text{H-O}}$ distance less than 3.00 \AA and the $d_{\text{H-O}}$ distance more than 3.00 \AA indicates at that position H-bonding interaction is not formed²⁷. This justifies the importance of both interaction energy between these molecules and CB[7] necessary to ensure a better complex of the guest to the host. The above values are substantiated by the fact that the flexibility of the host molecule may be one of the structural requirements for complexes formation. The present calculations explain that hydrogen bonding brings the difference between the binding energies of CB[7] complexation with these molecules. Note that the hydrogen-

bonding interaction of the carbonyl oxygen of the CB[7] molecule with bulk water molecules could provide an additional frictional force to the complexes.

Selected geometrical parameters for CB[7] and *o*PA : CB[7], *m*PA : CB[7] and *p*PA : CB[7] complexes are reported in Table 3. The O1-C2, N3-C4, and C4-C4' bond distances are predicted to be $0.005\text{--}0.011 \text{ \AA}$ longer in the complexes than in the isolated CB[7] host. The C2-N3 and C4-H2 bond distances of the glycouril units of CB[7] move closer on complexation, while the remaining bond distances in the glycouril monomer are almost unchanged. Interaction between the amino group of the PAs and CB[7] leads to significant distortion of the host cavity. The bond angles N3-C2-N5' change by less than 2 \AA upon complexation and C2-N3-C4, N3-C4-C4' in the complexes change by more than 7 \AA upon complexation. The alterations are also significant in all dihedral angles in the complexes, which indicate that the PAs must adopt a specific conformation to form weak complexes.

Table 3. Selected bond distances (in \AA) and bond angles (in $^\circ$) in CB[7], *o*PA : CB[7], *m*PA : CB[7] and *p*PA : CB[7]

Properties	CB[7]	<i>o</i> PA : CB[7]	<i>m</i> PA : CB[7]	<i>p</i> PA : CB[7]
Bond length (\AA)				
O1-C2	1.207	1.212	1.213	1.213
C2-N3	1.488	1.458	1.448	1.448
N3-C3	1.482	1.482	1.481	1.481
N3-C4	1.492	1.501	1.499	1.501
C4-C4'	1.554	1.561	1.565	1.565
C3-H1	1.110	1.111	1.110	1.110
C4-H2	1.130	1.119	1.119	1.119
C3-H3	1.111	1.111	1.111	1.111
Bond angle ($^\circ$)				
O1-C2-N3	124.51	125.71	125.89	125.87
C2-N3-C3	119.61	118.43	119.65	119.36
C2-N3-C4	101.97	108.57	108.67	108.66
N3-C4-C4'	100.42	105.04	104.56	104.61
N3-C2-N5'	110.54	108.60	108.83	108.90
C3-N3-C4	119.79	117.11	118.53	118.58
N3-C4-N5	125.83	114.46	115.13	115.07
Dihedral angle ($^\circ$)				
O1-C2-N3-C3	-28.43	-34.10	-23.02	-24.54
O1-C2-N5'-C5'	-57.54	-13.69	-28.03	-28.11
C2-N3-C4-N5	-150.54	-127.04	-130.72	-130.24
C2-N3-C4-C4'	40.44	13.92	16.40	16.08
C2-N3-C3-H3	-17.70	-4.96	-5.73	-4.62

In the host-guest system, the selective recognition depends on the size of the cavity, the cavity forces and the role of cavity sites, as well as the size and structural features of guest molecules. First, the size of host cavity must match the volume of guest molecules, especially in the condition of forming inclusion complexes. Second, strong supramolecular interactions, such as the hydrogen bonding, hydrophobic, electrostatic interaction, van der Waals forces, π - π effect etc., must exist to stabilize host-guest complexes²⁸⁻³². These intermolecular forces are mainly associated with the formation of three-dimensional structure, charge distribution and type of functional groups. In our cases, the benzene ring stabilizes the binding of CB[7] on the internal middle sites and directs the host to reach the guest nucleus, while the amino group stabilizes the CB[7] host when it bonds to the external sites and their hydrophilic character will obstruct CB[7] host from sliding to include the guest nucleus.

Conclusion

Using electronic structure calculations, the type of interactions present between CB[7] and PAs have been systematically investigated. The stoichiometric ratio of the complexes is 1 : 1. PAs forms weak inclusion complex with CB[7]. The CB[7] host molecule shows a slight geometrical flexibility in PAs binding which allows an induced fit of the PAs. In the complex, these molecules are found to be deep inside the cavity, with the formation of hydrogen bonding between the portal oxygen atom of carbonyl group and hydrogen atom of the amino group of the guest molecules. The HOMO is localized on the benzene ring and the LUMO is localized on the cucurbituril unit in the PAs : CB[7] complexes. Theoretical studies suggest that hydrophobic interaction and hydrogen bonding interaction play a key role in determining the stability of the inclusion complexes.

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